

The Global Issues That Matter the World

Mohammed Saaida

Department of International Relations and Diplomacy, Faculty of Administration Sciences and Informatics, Al-Istiqlal University, Jericho – Palestine.

Email: confador@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7488-9832>

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Abstract:

This paper gives a quick light spot on global issues. These issues are touched in everyday life. Anyone found on earth must be facing at least one of them. The major ecological and improvement issues are facing the cutting edge world. Spreading over disciplines like political theory, financial matters, social science, biology, global relations, and improvement studies, this famous reading material empowers understudies to foster an expansive point of view on the connections between countries, society, companies, and the climate in different settings. Investigating issues encompassing riches, destitution, imbalance, environmental change, normal assets, contamination, innovation, and others, the text represents the significance of worldwide answers for the issues confronting progressively reliant countries all over the planet. The researcher went through a briefing on several global issues, but not all of them. All of the global issues are related to each other in a series. The researcher found that the main cause of it is the economical factor. It starts here. The researcher recommends finding alternative ways for making life easier through friendly environmental ways of living. What do we need more?

Keywords: Climate change, Pollution, Lack of Primary Education, Unemployment, Food security, Health issues, Water scarcity.

Introduction:

In today's increasingly interconnected world, global issues have become a critical concern for nations, organizations, and individuals alike. The state of our planet and its inhabitants is threatened by a range of pressing challenges, from climate change and pollution to lack of primary education, unemployment, food security, health issues, and

water scarcity. These issues transcend borders and boundaries, affecting people from all walks of life and having far-reaching consequences for the future of humanity.

Climate change, for instance, is one of the most pressing issues of our time, with rising temperatures, melting glaciers, and extreme weather events threatening the stability of ecosystems and the livelihoods of millions of people. Similarly, pollution from industrial activities, transportation, and other sources is poisoning our air, water, and soil, causing widespread health problems and damaging the environment.

Other issues, such as lack of primary education, unemployment, food security, health issues, and water scarcity, are equally pressing. Without access to quality education, millions of children are denied the opportunity to reach their full potential, perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality. Meanwhile, unemployment and underemployment continue to plague many communities, leaving individuals and families struggling to make ends meet. Food security remains a major concern, with many regions facing chronic hunger and malnutrition, while health issues such as infectious diseases and mental health disorders afflict people everywhere. Finally, water scarcity threatens the very foundation of human survival, as growing populations and changing climates put increasing pressure on already strained water resources.

In the face of these daunting challenges, it is clear that individual actions alone are not enough. Instead, we need collective action and cooperation at all levels – local, national, and global – to address these issues and create a more sustainable, equitable, and prosperous future for all. By raising awareness, advocating for policy changes, and supporting innovative solutions, we can work together to overcome these global issues and build a better world for generations to come.

Main Global Issues

By the start the third decade of the second millennium, global issues still need much more to be done, despite all humble progress made. This examined how the world's countries did or did not work together to deal with critical challenge, domestically and throughout borders. Driven by their national interests, all of governments assist themselves only. The international cooperation hangs in the balance at precisely the moment when strong collaboration is wanted most from promoting climate change and sustainability to avoiding conflicts between nations to confronting the systematic forces that create

unequal societies. Here is the list of most important issues of nowadays that the world is facing.

1. Climate change

Climate change is widely regarded as one of the most pressing issues of our time, with many scholars arguing that the world is at a critical juncture in terms of transitioning climate patterns that threaten food production and rising sea levels, which increase the likelihood of devastating floods. For instance, consider the recent floods in Southeast Asian countries such as India, Australia, the Philippines, Bangladesh, and others. Additionally, the consequences of climate change are global in scope and of extraordinary magnitude.

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's (IPCC) latest fifth report, global temperatures have risen significantly from 1880 to 2012, with estimates suggesting that they will continue to rise by 2.6 degrees Celsius to 4.8 degrees Celsius by 2100. As a result, ice caps are melting and sea levels are rising, leading to more frequent and intense heat waves. Furthermore, the IPCC predicts that the Arctic could become ice-free within the next century, presenting a complex dilemma for society where economic growth through carbon-intensive activities must be balanced against efforts to reduce carbon emissions and mitigate the effects of climate change.

In light of these challenges, it is essential to prioritize sustainable development strategies that address both the need for economic growth and the imperative of reducing carbon emissions. By investing in renewable energy sources, implementing efficient technologies, and promoting environmentally conscious policies, nations can work towards achieving a more equitable and resilient future for all. Moreover, it is crucial to recognize the disproportionate impact of climate change on vulnerable communities, particularly those living in low-lying coastal areas, small island developing states, and arctic regions, and take steps to support their adaptation and resilience efforts.

2. Pollution:

Pollution affects every aspect of our lives, from the air we breathe to the water we drink, the soil we walk on, and even the noise we hear. It has direct and indirect impacts on human health, reduces the quality of life, causes disturbances, and has terrible effects on nature, including loss of biodiversity and ecosystems.

Environmental pollution is closely linked to climate change, making it an international concern that requires cooperation among countries to combat it effectively. The United Nations, the most influential international organization in the world, recognizes pollution as "the presence of substances and heat in environmental media (air, water, land) whose nature, location, or quantity produces undesirable environmental effects."

One of the biggest challenges faced by governments around the world is developing legislation with an international dimension to tackle pollution. The United Nations could play a key role in this effort, bringing together countries to work together to address this global issue. By working together, we can find solutions to reduce pollution and protect the planet for future generations.

3. Lack of Primary Education:

The lack of primary education is a significant issue globally, with millions of children missing out on this fundamental right. According to UNICEF, every child deserves access to education, but despite international efforts over the past 15 years, there are still over 72 million children worldwide who cannot attend primary school due to economic and social barriers. These children are often marginalized and excluded from society, perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality.

Moreover, the quality of primary education is also a cause for concern. Many governments have inadequate educational plans, resulting in poor teaching standards and inadequate resources for schools. This further exacerbates the existing disparities and hinders the ability of children to receive a decent education. Addressing these issues requires a concerted effort from governments, NGOs, and the international community to ensure that all children have access to high-quality primary education, regardless of their background or socioeconomic status.

4. Unemployment:

Imagine a large group of people who can't earn cash to spend on their livelihood and save what is left. It is a very dire economic situation that has exacerbated negative consequences and effects. These human beings can't feed themselves and their families. Unemployment is a significant issue that affects individuals, families, and entire communities. It not only hampers economic growth but also leads to a decline in the standard of living.

The most important reason for unemployment is the mismanagement of countries in addressing the issues of national economies. Employment is necessary from two aspects, the first is economic growth forward, and the second is enabling employees to secure their living requirements. Other major causes of unemployment are population growth and slow economic growth. The COVID-19 pandemic has further aggravated the situation, causing many people to lose their jobs. To overcome this challenge, it is essential to address the root causes of unemployment and implement effective solutions to create job opportunities and stimulate economic growth.

5. Food security:

There has been an increase in the number of hungry people in the world over the previous few years. United Nations reports show that one in nine humans in the world suffers from starvation and malnutrition. In addition, 11 percent of the world's population suffers from malnutrition due to a lack of food per capita or pollution. The problem is not that people do not produce enough food, but that a large number of them do not have enough cash to buy food. Moreover, they cannot farm for themselves according to the world food program. There is a close link between migration and lack of food, as the countries that export the most refugees and migrants have the highest rates of poverty, hunger and malnutrition.

6. Health issues:

There are many problems that affect health on a global scale. For example, the world has passed through the Corona pandemic. No sooner it had ended then it appeared again. The disease has infected more than 554 million human beings worldwide and caused the death of more than 6 million of them. Previously, the most important subject of focus was infectious diseases such as hepatitis, cholera, malaria, tuberculosis and HIV. Currently, the importance of the cooperation between all countries for the sake of achieving a strong cohesion in the face of the disease and its challenges. So that, this cooperation ought to be far from everything that might weakens it such as politics, financial profit and racial discrimination. The challenge does not stop here, but also teaching desirable hygiene practices. Emphasize the importance of proper nutritional education and prevention of personal harm. For many diseases that are still after many advances in medical fields. Several infectious diseases are still responsible for 71 death cases globally.

7. Water scarcity:

It is true that water covers about 70 percentage of the planet and it is easy to suppose that it will continually be abundant, but most of it is salt water. This means that it is not useful for ordinary human consumption in homes in its natural form, which is full of salt, impurities and microorganisms. Fresh water that humans use for drinking, bathing and farming is not available in most regions where people live. It constitutes only 3 percent of all water in the world. There is little fresh water available for use compared to what is held by the Arctic, Antarctic and frozen glaciers.

Worldwide, 1.1 billion humans lack access to clean water; the problem is that the need for human use for industry and agriculture for food production increases every year. Complicating matters further is the issue of climate change. Currently, the world is witnessing actual changes in the quantities of water available. We can take Italy right now as a country with the worst drought in 70 years.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the global issues that matter the world today are numerous and interconnected, posing significant threats to the well-being of humans and the planet. Climate change, pollution, lack of primary education, unemployment, food security, health issues, and water scarcity are just a few examples of the pressing concerns that demand urgent attention and collective action from governments, businesses, civil society, and individuals across the globe.

These issues are complex and multifaceted, requiring a coordinated approach that addresses their underlying causes and promotes sustainable solutions. From investing in renewable energy and reducing carbon emissions to improving access to education and healthcare, and fostering sustainable agriculture and water management practices, there is much that can be done to mitigate the impact of these issues and create a more equitable and prosperous future for all.

However, achieving these goals will require more than just technical solutions; it will also necessitate a shift in values and priorities, as well as a willingness to engage in open and inclusive dialogue, and to take bold and collective action. As individuals, we can start by educating ourselves about these issues, advocating for policies and practices that promote sustainability and social justice, and making conscious choices in our daily lives that support a more equitable and environmentally responsible

future. Together, we can create a world that is more resilient, more equitable, and more sustainable for all.

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